

INNOVATIVE MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article highlights the great importance attached to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the issues of increasing the effectiveness of education through the use of innovative technologies and methods necessary for their study.*

Keywords: *foreign language, games, innovative technologies, technological tools, teaching methods.*

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich said: “At present, in our country, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages”. This is of course not in vain. Today there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect command of foreign languages for our country’s youth, striving to take their rightful place in the world community, and for our people, building their great future in solidarity and cooperation. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European System of Teaching Foreign Languages and Assessing the Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and higher educational institutions. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication technology. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing every day. The science of foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are the effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also envisaged to improve the quality and efficiency of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are a number of advantages of using such information and communication technologies when learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in learning and teaching languages is incomparable. The use of technological tools is beneficial in all aspects of foreign language learning (reading, writing, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CDs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker’s pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students are well aware of information and communication technologies and know how to use them.

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. The use of gaming technologies is based on activities that activate and accelerate the learner. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of gaming activity are based on the fundamental human needs for self-expression, finding a stable place in life, self-control, and realizing one’s potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on academic subjects. During games,

the teacher is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a teaching method. Students participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher, through them, also ensures the education of the student. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand and write in English during the game, he is interested in it.

We know that in the modern educational process the subject must be the teacher. More emphasis on interactive methods will improve the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English classes is to teach students to think for themselves. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods based on the experience of teachers in the USA and England:

- To use this Creative Problem-Solving method, the beginning of the story is read and the end of the story is shared with the students;

- “Funny riddles”, solving riddles by schoolchildren is important when teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to the riddle;

- “Quick answers” help increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

- “Warm-up exercises” using various games in the lesson to interest students in the lesson;

- “Pantomime”. This method can be used in a lesson where it is necessary to explain very difficult topics or when written exercises are being performed and the students are tired;

- The “Chain Story” method helps students develop oral speech;

- The “Acting Characters” method can be used in all types of lessons. For the purpose of teaching the profession, people of such professions as “Translator”, “Writer”, “Poet” can participate in classes and talk with students;

- Such poets and writers as W. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be “invited” to the “meeting of thinkers”. At such a time, the use of wise words spoken in the lesson will help young people to be raised into perfect people;

- The “When Pictures Speak” method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop students’ oral speech; for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;

- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

Conclusion

All such methods provide for the cooperation of teacher and student, the active action of the student in the educational process. In a word, as a result of using innovative methods in English lessons, students develop logical thinking skills, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods create a desire for knowledge in students. The student tries to thoroughly prepare for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

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